

Verifying Correctness of PLC Software during System Evolution using Model Containment Approach

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Abstract. Upgradation of Programmable Logic Controller (PLC) software is quite common to accommodate evolving industrial requirements. Verifying the correctness of such upgrades remains a significant challenge. In this paper, we propose a verification-based approach to ensure the correctness of the existing functionality in the upgraded version of a PLC software. The method converts the older and the newer versions of the sequential function chart (SFC) into two Petri net models. We then verify whether one model is contained within another, based on a novel containment checking algorithm grounded in symbolic path equivalence. For this purpose, we have developed a home-grown Petri net-based containment checker. Experimental evaluation on 80 real-world benchmarks from the OSCAT library highlights the scalability and effectiveness of the framework. We have compared our approach with `verifAPS`, a popular tool used for software upgradation, and observed nearly 4x performance improvement.

Keywords: Petri net, PLC software verification, industrial automation, Sequential Function Chart (SFC), containment checking, software evolution.

1 Introduction

A modern automation system is driven by process control software written in various programmable logic controller (PLC) languages. To remain efficient, reliable, and sustainable, existing software must be continually upgraded to meet evolving market demands and new safety regulations. However, modifying PLC software carries far more risks, particularly unintended regressions may disrupt existing process operations, leading to disastrous consequences. Therefore, ensuring the correctness of upgraded PLC software is extremely critical.

Traditional approaches to PLC software regression testing primarily rely on simulation and regression tests, which can be time-consuming, incomplete, and dependent on domain-specific expertise. While regression testing is commonly

employed to compare outputs before and after software modifications, it may not always capture behavioral discrepancies introduced during upgrades.

In this paper, we propose a novel verification-based approach that formally ensures the correctness of existing functionality in the upgraded PLC software. Here, we consider a popular IEC 61131-3 compliant PLC language known as the Sequence Function Chart (SFC). We transform both the older and newer versions of the SFC into Petri net models and verify whether one model is contained in the other. This containment check is based on the notion of behavioral equivalence, ensuring that the upgraded version preserves the expected execution behavior of the previous version. The contributions of our paper are as follows.

1. Model Enhancement- We present an improved version of the Petri net model, where a place can have a sequence of functions (instead of a single function in[1, 2]), while transitions are now limited to guard conditions only. This refinement leads to a more compact model representation. We further propose the notion of *execution cut point* to handle PLC tick semantics.
2. Petri Net-based Model Construction – We introduce a model transformation process that converts an SFC program into a Petri net in order to compare behaviors across versions. The transformation process handles synchronous execution semantics through tick labeling, which is crucial for PLC verification but not addressed in general Petri net approaches.
3. Containment Checking Tool – We defined a new theoretical foundation of *containment* and proposed an algorithm to check containment of one Petri net in another. This, in turn, verifies behavioral consistency between different software versions.
4. Scalability and Practical Evaluation – We validate our approach on a diverse set of eighty benchmarks from the open-source OSCAT library, demonstrating its effectiveness in real-world PLC software evolution scenarios. We have also compared our approach with the popular open-source `verifAPS` tool.

The paper has been organized as follows. Section 2 introduces a motivating use-case as a running example in the paper. Section 3 describes the functional architecture of the proposed tool. Section 4 illustrates the construction of a Petri net model. We describe the containment checking process in Section 5. We report the experimental evaluation of the tool in Section 6. We discuss the utility and limitations of our approach in Section 7. Section 8 discusses several important relevant contributions in this area. Finally, we conclude our paper.

2 Motivating Example

Within this paper, we employ a widely recognized “Pick and Place system” [3] as an ongoing example. The system outlined is a simplified representation of a complex industrial process where items are initially placed on Conveyor A. A robotic arm then simultaneously transfers two items from Conveyor A to Conveyor B. Conveyor B is equipped with a scaling sensor that verifies the scaling parameters of these items, denoted as a and b . When these parameters are

Fig. 1. Pick and Place System- original and upgraded version with safety features

positive, a fixer combines them, and a second robotic arm deposits the composite item into the green *Collect Bin*. Conversely, if the parameters fail to meet a positive value, the items are put to the red *Waste Bin*. The fixing process hinges on intricate calculations adjusting individual scaling factors of items a and b to derive an integrated, custom scaling metric.

In its upgraded version, the system includes a newly installed safety guard sensor, complying with the latest safety protocol (ISO 10218-1)³. This sensor oversees the overall system operation and ensures that, without the safety guard being active, the robotic arm on Conveyor A remains immobilized, preventing any object transfer from Conveyor A to B due to breach of safety norms. If the safety guard is *in place*, the robot will place the objects on the conveyor belt B, and the scaling sensor will check the scaling parameters as in the original version. Furthermore, the upgraded version computes the fine-tuning of the individual scaling factors (for a and b) concurrently. The classical testing method is not useful for two reasons.

1. An SFC software testing generally takes 3 to 5 minutes by an expert engineer in a testing environment.
2. The older version is purely sequential, whereas the upgraded version has parallelism, as it performs the scaling computation concurrently.

The entire control logic is implemented in SFC. The SFC for Figure 3(a) is in Figure 4(c), and for the upgraded version in Figure 3(b), it is shown in Figure 4(d).

3 Containment Checking Software

The containment verification tool illustrated in Figure 2 includes three key components: the Petri net model constructor, the Model Analyzer, and the Report Generator. As detailed in Section 4, the Petri net model constructor transforms an SFC program into a Petri net model. *Petri nets are selected as the formal model due to their semantics being well-aligned with those of Sequential Function Charts (SFC) [4], facilitating a more intuitive and precise translation. Conversely, converting SFC to a Control Data Flow Graph (CDFG) entails multiple intermediate transformations [5], increasing the modeling complexity. The*

³ <https://www.iso.org/standard/73933.html>

Fig. 2. Functional Block Diagram

Path constructor component generates an array of paths derived from a set of cut-points to a cut-point without any intermediary cut-points. The Model Containment Checker component takes two Petri net models—one for the original SFC code and the other for the updated SFC code—to determine if the updated SFC retains the original SFC’s functionality. This process is referred to as model containment checking (Definitions 7 and 6). This component leverages data transformation and an execution condition checker to assess model containment. We incorporate the concept of path equivalence checking [1] for this purpose. The report generator module delivers a comprehensive textual explanation of how two SFC codes meet the containment requirements, and if there is a violation, it explains why the containment relationship does not hold.

4 Petri net based Containment Checking

Fig. 3. Two versions of Pick and Place, (a) Original SFC (b) Upgraded SFC (changes shown in blue color)

An SFC code is comparable to a Petri net; formally described in [6]. We reproduce the definition for brevity.

Definition 1. A sequential function chart (SFC) $\mathcal{S} = \langle S, X, A, T_S, s_0 \rangle$, is a structure where S is a finite set of steps, X is a finite set of variables, A is a finite set of actions, T_S is a finite set of transitions for SFC, and s_0 is the initial step.

Let Σ_{SFC} be the all possible states for variable in X , i.e., $\Sigma_{SFC} = \{\sigma | \sigma : X \rightarrow Value\}$ where σ assigns a $val \in Value$ to each variable in X . Next, $a_N \in A$ is an action, modeled as a state transformation function $\mathcal{T} : \Sigma_{SFC} \rightarrow \Sigma_{SFC}$.

A **block** is an action labeling function that assigns to each step a collection of pairs $\langle a_N, q \rangle$, referred to as an action block, where a_N is an action and $q \in \{entry, active, exit\}$ denotes an action qualifier. We consider the qualifiers *entry*: to indicate computation during the entry of the step, *exit*: to indicate computation during the exit of the step, and *active*: to indicate computation when the step is active. There is a flow relation between a *step* to a *transition* and a *transition* to a *step*. Each transition $t \in T_S$ is associated with a *guard condition* g_s which is a boolean function over a subset of the variables in X .

SFC semantics contains a global time, modeled by a *tick*⁴ [7]. Computation in the *active* step happens at each *tick* value. After the computation, the *tick* value is incremented. We do not consider hierarchical SFCs in this work, where actions may also contain another SFC.

Example 1. Figures 3(a) and 3(b) are SFC programs for the original and the upgraded version of the pick and place system (Figure 1), respectively. In Figure 3(a), $S = \{s_0, \dots, s_{10}\}$, $T_S = \{Tr_1, \dots, Tr_{14}\}$. Every step $s \in S$ is associated with an action sequence. The action sequence for s_7 is **a= a*10**, followed by **b=b/10** and then **I++**. Every transition has a guard condition. In Figure 3(a), the guard condition associated with Tr_4 is F_{x_1} and Tr_{12} is $\neg F_{x_1}$. Here F_{x_1} denotes the expression $Fixer > 0$. If no guard condition is explicitly associated with a transition, it is treated as *true*.

In Figure 3(a), the SFC starts from step s_0 , with the action **WAIT=T**, while all other actions are false. The sensor L_1 represents a load sensor on conveyor belt A. When an object is detected on this conveyor, L_1 becomes true, enabling transition Tr_1 and progressing to s_1 , with update actions **RUN=T**, **WAIT=F**, and $C_1 = T$.

Next, with the activation of the guard condition $C_1 = T$, transition Tr_2 is enabled, leading to s_2 . Here, the robotic arm picks the object from conveyor belt A, and C_1 is set to false (**RUN=F**, **PICK=T**, and $C_1 = F$).

When the guard condition for transition Tr_3 is true, the system enters s_3 where the object is transferred from conveyor belt A to B, and the action **PLACE=T** is set. During this placement, the robotic arm also checks the scaling parameter value using a sensor attached to the arm. If the scaling parameter is positive, they are fixed by a fixer, via step s_4 and the object is placed in the collection bin at s_8 . Otherwise, the object is sent to the waste bin through step s_9 .

In the upgraded version shown in Figure 3(b), an additional safety sensor (S) monitors the system's status. If the safety guard is *false*, the robot arm of Conveyor A remains locked, preventing the robot from transferring any object from Conveyor A to B. Instead, all objects are redirected to the waste bin via step s'_{13} . Additionally, the custom scaling process is now carried out in parallel.

⁴ <https://control.com/technical-articles/an-overview-of-iec-61131-3-Industrial-Automation-Systems/>

The blue-colored portion in Figure 3(b) indicate the upgraded portions of the SFC. ■

Definition 2. A Petri net model is a 7-tuple $N = \langle P, V, F, T, I, O, P_{M_0} \rangle$, where P is a finite non-empty set of places, V is a set of variables, F be set of all update functions, T is a finite non-empty set of transitions, $I \subset P \times T$ is a finite non-empty set of input arcs which define the flow relation between places and transitions, $O \subset T \times P$ is a finite non-empty set of output arcs which define the flow relation between transitions and places and P_{M_0} is the initial set of place marking.

Each place is associated with a set of variables using the function $\phi : P \rightarrow 2^V$. Each element of V belongs to one of two disjoint subsets, namely the set of changed variables (V_c) or the set of unchanged variables (V_u). Here we only consider integer and boolean types. Each place is associated with a sequence of update functions $F_p \subseteq F$ for the variables in V where each function is of the form $\Sigma_{PN} \rightarrow \Sigma_{PN}$ such that Σ_{PN} represents set of all possible states of variable in V .

A place can hold a *token*. A place with a token is called a *marked place*. When a place is *marked*, it computes a sequence of functions associated with it. The corresponding values of the variables, as defined by these functions, are updated.

Each transition t is associated with a *guard condition* g_t , a boolean function over a subset of the variables. A transition t is said to be *enabled* when all its pre-place(s) have token(s), and they are associated with the set(s) of values of the variable which satisfy g_t . All the enabled transitions can fire simultaneously, which in turn models parallel execution. A transition $t_s \in T$ is said to be a *synchronizing transition* if its post-places are all the initial marked places. Our Petri net model is deterministic and 1-safe (at any point in time, a place contains at most one token, but one token corresponds to k variables).

4.1 SFC to Petri net translation

Translating an SFC into a Petri net is syntactic and straightforward, where one can generate a Petri net in a single pass over the SFC structure. The Petri net model's entities I and O correspond to the SFC's flow relation. The mapping of SFC entities to Petri net entities is $S \rightarrow P$, $X \rightarrow V$, $T_s \rightarrow T$, $g_s \rightarrow g_t$, $s_0 \rightarrow P_{M_0}$, and $A \rightarrow F$. Note that the action names for each action block in the SFC are executed in the same order as the functions in F_p in the Petri net, with both following the ordering defined by the action qualifier in the order of *entry*, *active*, and *exit* for the particular action block.

For any *state-modifying action* (e.g., incrementing a variable) associated with a step in a Sequential Function Chart (SFC), the corresponding Petri net sub-net can be modeled as follows:

1. A *place* p represents the corresponding *SFC step* in the Petri net.
2. This place is connected to two *mutually exclusive transitions*.
3. One of these transitions, denoted t_u , models the execution of the state-modifying action. It forms a self-loop with p , represented by the flow relations (p, t_u) and (t_u, p) .
4. The transition t_u is enabled under the *negation of the condition* that enables the alternative transition.
5. All enabled transitions in the Petri net contain the same *tick* value

4.2 Computation and Containment of Petri net model

Before describing the containment checking in this subsection, we describe the prerequisites of the Petri net model related to computational equivalence.

Definition 3 (Successor marking). *A set of marked places P_{M^+} is said to be a successor place marking of P_M , if P_{M^+} includes all post-places of transitions T_M enabled by P_M . and also all the places of P_M whose post-transitions are not enabled; symbolically, $P_{M^+} = \{p \mid p \in t^\circ \text{ and } t \in T_M\} \cup \{p \mid p \in P_M \text{ and } p \notin {}^\circ T_M\}$.*

Definition 4 (Computation). *In a Petri net model N with initial marked places P_{M_0} , a computation μ_p of an out-port p (place having a synchronizing transition) is a sequence $\langle T_1, T_2, \dots, T_i, \dots, T_l \rangle$ of sets of maximally parallelizable transitions [1] satisfying the following properties:*

1. *There exists a sequence of markings of places $\langle P_{M_0}, P_{M_1}, \dots, P_{M_{l-1}} \rangle$ such that*
 - (a) *P_{M_0} be the set of initial marked places*
 - (b) *$\forall i, 1 \leq i < l$, P_{M_i} is a successor place marking of $P_{M_{i-1}}$, ${}^\circ T_i \subseteq P_{M_{i-1}}$ and $T_i^\circ \subseteq P_{M_i}$.*
2. *$p \in T_l^\circ$.*

There are two entities associated with every computation: (1) the condition of execution denoted as R_{μ_p} and (2) the data transformation denoted as r_{μ_p} ; both are expressed in normalized form [8].

Definition 5 (Equivalence of a Computation). Let N_0 and N_1 be two Petri net models with their set of initial place marking bijection f_{in} and out-port bijection f_{out} . A computation μ_p of a model N_0 having an out-port p is said to be equivalent to a computation $\mu_{p'}$ of another model N_1 having an out-port p' such that $f_{out}(p) = p'$, symbolically denoted as $\mu_p \simeq_c \mu_{p'}$, if $R_{\mu_p} \equiv R_{\mu_{p'}}$ and $r_{\mu_p} = r_{\mu_{p'}}$.

Definition 6 (Containment of two models). The Petri net model N_0 is said to be contained in the Petri net model N_1 , represented as $N_0 \sqsubseteq N_1$, if, $\forall p \in$ out-port of N_0 , for any computation μ_p of p , \exists a computation $\mu_{p'}$ of an out-port $p' = f_{out}(p)$ of N_1 such that $\mu_p \simeq_c \mu_{p'}$.

Definition 7 (Equivalence of two models). A model N_0 is said to be computationally equivalent to a model N_1 , symbolically denoted as $N_0 \simeq N_1$, if $N_0 \sqsubseteq N_1$ and $N_1 \sqsubseteq N_0$.

In symbolic computation-based program equivalence checking, a loop is cut to create a cut-point. Then, a path α is constructed from one cut-point to another without any intermediary cut-points such that *any computation can be represented as a concatenation of paths* [9–12].

The notion of cut-points and paths has been adopted in Petri-net based models [1, 2] as *static cut-points* for program equivalence checking. We revisit these concepts here since our approach is also built upon the general notion of cut-points and paths. Static cut-points are introduced in initial marked places, places with multiple post-transitions, places containing back edges, and out-ports. This enables us to break the model into a finite set of paths between these cut-points. The symbol $^\circ\alpha$ denotes the set of places where the path α originates.

Like computation (Definition 4), every path α is associated with two entities: 1) the condition of execution along the path, denoted as R_α and 2) the data transformation along the path r_α . For example, consider Figure 4(c). For the path α_1 , $R_{\alpha_1} = L_1 \rightsquigarrow C_1 \rightsquigarrow \neg C_1$, and $r_{\alpha_1} = \{\text{RUN}=\text{F}, \text{PICK}=\text{F}, \text{PLACE}=\text{T}, \text{WAIT}=\text{F}, C_1 = \text{F}, \text{Fixer}\}$. The WFF constructor component (Figure 1) stores these expressions in the normalized form [8].

While a static cut-point is a handy tool to model a computation, it is not sufficient when a computation involves an unknown number of loop traversals, as explained Example 2.

Example 2. Let us consider the computation in Figure 5. The set of static cut-points is $\{p_1, p_7, p_{10}\}$ and the paths will be $\alpha_1 = \langle \{t_1\}, \{t_2\}, \{t_4\}, \{t_6\}, \{t_7\} \rangle$, $\alpha_2 = \langle \{t_1\}, \{t_3\}, \{t_5\} \rangle$, $\alpha_3 = \langle \{t_8\}, \{t_9\} \rangle$ and $\alpha_4 = \langle \{t_s\} \rangle$. Let us consider a computation μ of the out-port p_{10} , where $\mu = \langle T_1 = \{t_1\}, T_2 = \{t_2, t_3\}, T_3 = \{t_4, t_5\}, T_4 = \{t_6, t_8\}, (T_5 = \{t_9\}, T_6 = \{t_8\}, T_5 = \{t_9\})^n, T_7 = \{t_7\}, T_8 = \{t_{10}\} \rangle$. Since t_{10} (in α_1) and t_8 (in α_3) are mutually exclusive transitions and can't execute in parallel, α_1 and α_3 need to be concatenated in any computation, hence in μ as well. However, *There does not exist any concatenation of paths $\{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3\}$ that can express this computation μ due to the transition group T_4 .* T_4 has transitions $\{t_6, t_8\}$ which execute in parallel. However, t_6 is a part of the

Fig. 5. A Petri net model of a computation involving loops

path α_1 , and t_8 belongs to α_3 . As a result, α_1, α_3 cannot be concatenated in any order.

However, if we had p_6, p_7, p_8, p_9 and p_{11} also as cut-points, the path-set would have been $\alpha'_1 = \langle \{t_1\}, \{t_2\}, \{t_4\} \rangle$, $\alpha'_2 = \langle \{t_1\}, \{t_3\}, \{t_5\} \rangle$, $\alpha'_3 = \langle \{t_6\} \rangle$, $\alpha'_4 = \langle \{t_7\} \rangle$, $\alpha'_5 = \langle \{t_8\} \rangle$, $\alpha'_6 = \langle \{t_9\} \rangle$ and $\alpha'_7 = \langle \{t_{10}\} \rangle$ (green boundaries in Figure 5). Now, intuitively, the computation μ can be depicted as the sequence $(\alpha'_1 \parallel \alpha'_2) \cdot (\alpha_3 \parallel \alpha'_5) \cdot (\alpha'_6 \cdot \alpha'_5)^n \cdot \alpha'_4 \cdot \alpha'_7$ of concatenation of parallelizable paths from the set $\{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4, \alpha_5, \alpha_6, \alpha_7\}$, where $(\alpha_1 \parallel \alpha_2)$ means parallel execution of α_1 and α_2 and $(\alpha_1 \cdot \alpha_2)$ means sequential execution α_1 followed by α_2 . ■

The concept of *Dynamic cut-points* was introduced [2] to overcome the drawbacks associated with static cut-point based computation, as demonstrated in Example 2. Although dynamic cut-points are more suitable for our use case, they were originally crafted for procedural languages such as C. In the context of synchronous reactive systems like SFC, which feature the concept of *ticks*, we have expanded the dynamic cut-point framework to include ticks. We call this the *Execution cut-point*, defined below.

Definition 8 (Execution cut-point). A place p is designated as a *Execution cut-point* if, during a token tracking execution of the model [13] (with static cut-points already incorporated), a place marking P_M containing p is encountered such that one of the following conditions is satisfied:

1. P_M contains at least one cut-point; or
2. P_M contains more places than its pre-transitions \mathcal{T}_M whose tick values are identical, i.e., $|P_M| > |\circ P_M| \wedge \circ P_M = \{t \in \mathcal{T}_M \mid \text{tick}(t) = v\}$, where v is a fixed tick value common to all $t \in \mathcal{T}_M$; this indicates that the token tracking execution has reached a point of creation of some parallel threads.

Henceforth, both static and execution cut-points will be collectively referred to as cut-points for simplicity.

Definition 9 (Path cover). A finite set of paths $\Pi = \{\alpha_0, \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_k\}$ is said to be a *path cover* of a Petri net model N if any computation μ of an out-port of N can be represented as a sequence of concatenations of parallelizable paths from Π .

The definition of the parallelizable path and the concatenation of a path, along with its characteristic, is reported in [2].

Definition 10 (Place, Transition and Variable correspondence). Let N_0 and N_1 be two Petri net models with their initial marked places bijection f_{in} and out-port bijection f_{out} . Equivalence of paths of N_0 and N_1 , a transition correspondence relation, denoted as $\eta_t \subseteq T_0 \times T_1$, and a place correspondence relation, denoted as $\eta_p \subseteq P_0 \times P_1$, are defined as follows:

1. $f_{in} \subseteq \eta_p$,
2. Two paths α of N_0 and β of N_1 are said to be equivalent, denoted as $\alpha \simeq \beta$, if $\forall p \in {}^\circ\alpha$, there exists exactly one $p' \in {}^\circ\beta$ such that $\phi^0(p) = \phi^1(p')$, $\langle p, p' \rangle \in \eta_p$, $R_\alpha(\phi^0({}^\circ\alpha)) \equiv R_\beta(\phi^1({}^\circ\beta))$, $r_\alpha(\phi^0({}^\circ\alpha)) = r_\beta(\phi^1({}^\circ\beta))$ and $TickStamp(last(\alpha)) = TickStamp(last(\beta))$. Note that $last(\alpha)$ indicates the last member of the path α .
3. For any two equivalent paths α, β , $\langle last(\alpha), last(\beta) \rangle \in \eta_t$ if their TickStamps are identical.
4. Let V_0 and V_1 be the set of variables for N_0 and N_1 respectively, and the variable correspondence relation η_v is defined as $\eta_v \subseteq ((V_0 - V_1) \times V_1) \cup (V_0 \times (V_1 - V_0))$; thus, if $\langle v, v' \rangle \in \eta_v$ then either $(v \in V_0) \wedge (v \notin V_1)$ or, $(v' \in V_1) \wedge (v' \notin V_0)$. Furthermore, for any two equivalent paths α of N_0 and β of N_1 , for any two places $p \in post$ place of $\alpha, p' \in post$ place of path β , $\langle p, p' \rangle \in \eta_p$ if
 - (a) $\phi^0(p) = \phi^1(p')$ or
 - (b) if $\phi^0(p) \in V_0 - V_1$ or $\phi^1(p') \in V_1 - V_0$ then
 - i. either $\langle \phi^0(p), \phi^1(p') \rangle$ have already been associated with each other in η_v , or
 - ii. they have not yet been associated with any other variables and can now be associated associated in η_v ; also $\langle p, p' \rangle$ is put in η_p ;

Theorem 1. A Petri net model N_0 is contained in another Petri net model N_1 , denoted as $N_0 \sqsubseteq N_1$, for all finite path cover $\Pi_0 = \{\alpha_0, \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_l\}$ of N_0 for which there exists a set $\Pi_1 = \{\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_l\}$ of paths of N_1 such that for all $i, 0 \leq i \leq l$, (i) $\alpha_i \simeq \beta_i$, (ii) the places in ${}^\circ\alpha_i$ have correspondence with those in ${}^\circ\beta_i$ and (iii) the places in α_i° have correspondence with those in β_i° .

The detailed proof is given in the Appendix.

5 Containment checking method

We describe the containment checking approach in Algorithm 1. We demonstrate the containment checking between two Petri nets N_0 and N_1 shown in Figures 4(c) and (d), respectively.

1. Step 1 of ContainmentChecker (Algorithm 1) accepts the user supplied place correspondence between the place p_0 of N_0 and the place p'_0 of N_1 to start the process.

Algorithm 1: ContainmentChecker(N_0, N_1)**Input:** Petri net models N_0 and N_1 **Output:** A six-tuple: (1) Π_0 : path cover of N_0 , (2) Π_1 : path cover of N_1 matching Π_0 , (3) E : set of $\langle \alpha, \beta \rangle$ such that $\alpha \simeq \beta$, (4) η_t : matched transition pairs, (5) $\Pi_{n,0}$: unmatched paths from N_0 , (6) $\Pi_{n,1}$: unmatched paths from N_1 1: $\eta_p \leftarrow \{ \langle p, p' \rangle \mid p \in P_{M_0} \wedge p' \in P'_{M_0} \wedge p' = f_{in}(p) \}; \quad \eta_t \leftarrow \emptyset$ 2: $\Pi'_0 \leftarrow \mathbf{PathConstructor}(N_0); \quad \Pi'_1 \leftarrow \mathbf{PathConstructor}(N_1)$ 3: Initialize $\Pi_0, \Pi_1, \Pi_{n,0}, \Pi_{n,1}, E$ to \emptyset 4: **for all** $\alpha \in \Pi'_0$ **do**5: Compute R_α and r_α 6: $\Gamma' = \mathbf{SelectedPathForCheckingEquivalence}(\alpha, \Pi'_1, \eta_t, f_{in})$ 7: **for all** $\beta \in \Gamma'$ **do**8: Remove all uncommon variables and then Compute R_β and r_β 9: **if** $(R_\alpha \simeq R_\beta) \wedge (r_\alpha == r_\beta) \wedge (\text{TickStamp}(\text{last}(\alpha)) == \text{TickStamp}(\text{last}(\beta)))$ **then**10: $\eta_t = \eta_t \cup \{ \langle \text{last}(\alpha), \text{last}(\beta) \rangle \}$ 11: $E = E \cup \{ \langle \alpha, \beta \rangle \}$ 12: $\Pi_0 = \Pi_0 \cup \{ \alpha \}; \quad \Pi'_0 = \Pi'_0 \setminus \{ \alpha \}$ 13: $\Pi_1 = \Pi_1 \cup \{ \beta \}; \quad \Pi'_1 = \Pi'_1 \setminus \{ \beta \}$ 14: $\eta_p = \eta_p \cup \{ \alpha^\circ, \beta^\circ \} \{ \beta \simeq \alpha \}$ 15: **else if** $((R_{\alpha_1} \lesssim R_{\beta_1}) \wedge (\text{TickStamp}(\text{last}(\alpha)) < \text{TickStamp}(\text{last}(\beta))) \vee (r_\alpha = \emptyset))$ **then**16: $\Pi_0 = \mathbf{prepareForExtension}(\alpha, \Pi_0, \Pi_{n,0}, \eta_t, E)$ // extend α 17: **else if** $((R_{\beta_1} \lesssim R_{\alpha_1}) \wedge (\text{TickStamp}(\text{last}(\alpha)) > \text{TickStamp}(\text{last}(\beta))) \vee (r_\beta = \emptyset))$ **then**18: $\Pi_1 = \mathbf{prepareForExtension}(\beta, \Pi_1, \Pi_{n,1}, \eta_t, E)$ // extend β 19: **else if** $(R_\beta \simeq R_\alpha) \wedge (\text{TickStamp}(\text{last}(\alpha)) \neq \text{TickStamp}(\text{last}(\beta))) \wedge (r_\alpha \neg = r_\beta)$ **then**20: $\Pi'_0 = \mathbf{prepareForMerging}(\Gamma)$ //merging operation through N_0 or N_1 21: **else if** $(R_\alpha \neg \simeq R_\beta)$ **then**22: $\Pi_{n,0} = \Pi_{n,0} \cup \{ \alpha \}$ 23: $\Pi_{n,1} = \Pi_{n,1} \cup \{ \beta \}$ 24: $\Pi'_0 = \Pi_0 \setminus \{ \alpha \}$ //Non-equivalent25: $\Pi'_1 = \Pi_1 \setminus \{ \beta \}$ //Non-equivalent26: **end if**27: **end for**28: **end for**29: **if** $\Pi_{n,0} = \emptyset \wedge \Pi_{n,1} = \emptyset$ **then**30: Report “ N_0 and N_1 are equivalent models.”31: **else if** $\Pi_{n,0} = \emptyset \wedge \Pi_{n,1} \neq \emptyset$ **then**32: Report “ $N_0 \sqsubseteq N_1$ and $N_1 \not\sqsubseteq N_0$.”33: **else if** $\Pi_{n,0} \neq \emptyset \wedge \Pi_{n,1} = \emptyset$ **then**34: Report “ $N_1 \sqsubseteq N_0$ and $N_0 \not\sqsubseteq N_1$.”35: **else**

36: Report “Two models may not be equivalent.”

37: **end if**38: **return** $\langle \Pi_0, \Pi_1, E, \eta_t, \Pi_{n,0}, \Pi_{n,1} \rangle$

2. Step 2 of Algorithm 1 invokes PathConstructor method (Algorithm 2 in Appendix) to generate the set of paths for both N_0 and N_1 as $\{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_8\}$ and $\{\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_{12}\}$, respectively. The dotted boundaries for N_0 and N_1 represent these paths. The PathConstructor method invokes Algorithm 3 (in Appendix) to generate execution cut-points and paths corresponding to these cut-points. For instance, the Algorithm 3 marked the place p_6 of N_0 and the places p'_7 and p'_9 of N_1 as *execution cut-points*.

3. (*Path Extension*): Step 6 of Algorithm 1 identifies a set of candidate paths in N_1 for a path α in N_0 . To begin with, the place correspondence between p_0 of N_0 and p'_0 of N_1 is considered. Accordingly, the path α_1 of N_0 is selected as the candidate path for β_1 of N_1 for equivalence checking. Since $R_{\alpha_1} \equiv L_1 \rightsquigarrow C_1 \rightsquigarrow \neg C_1$, and $R_{\beta_1} \equiv L_1$, $R_{\beta_1} \lesssim R_{\alpha_1}$. This is evaluated in step 17 of Algorithm 1 and *prepareForExtension* method (Algorithm 4 in Appendix) is called to extend β_1 .

Step 7 of Algorithm 4 computes the set of post paths, i.e., the successor path of β_1 to be β_2 . The execution condition of the concatenated path $(\beta_1.\beta_2)$ is $L_1 \rightsquigarrow C_1 \rightsquigarrow S \rightsquigarrow \neg C_1$. Since S is an uncommon variable, it is dropped and the resulting $R_{\beta_1.\beta_2} \equiv L_1 \rightsquigarrow C_1 \rightsquigarrow \neg C_1$. Now $R_{\alpha_1} \simeq R_{(\beta_1.\beta_2)}$ and $r_{\alpha_1} = r_{(\beta_1.\beta_2)}$. In the next iteration, step 9 of Algorithm 1 ensures $\alpha_1 \simeq (\beta_1.\beta_2)$, and the place correspondence between p_3 and p'_3 is established.

Similarly for the path α_2 , step 6 of Algorithm 1 selects the candidate path β_3 . In β_3 , both variables I and J are initialized to 0. Therefore, variable I corresponds to variable J . As a result, their execution conditions are equivalent, and the data transformations are the same. Hence, $\alpha_2 \simeq \beta_3$, and p_5 of N_0 corresponds to both p'_6 and p'_8 of N_1 (step 9 of Algorithm 1).

4. (*Path Merging*): The data transformation r_α is empty for the path α_3 in N_0 . Therefore, step 27 of Algorithm 1 asserts that it is necessary to extend α_3 until the data transformation becomes non empty. The post-path of α_3 is α_4 . The data transformation of the concatenated path $\alpha_e = (\alpha_3.\alpha_4)$ is $r_{\alpha_e} = (\mathbf{a}=\mathbf{a}*10, \mathbf{b}=\mathbf{b}/10, \mathbf{I}++)$. Recall that the WFF constructor component (Figure 1) the normalized form [8].

In the next iteration, step 6 selects candidate paths (from N_1) for this new path α_e , to be β_4 and β_7 . For the path β_4 , the execution condition matches; however, the data transformation does not, resulting in path merging (step 20 of Algorithm 1). We now explain how path merging works.

Step 4 of Algorithm 5 first computes the pre-path of β_4 which is β_3 , and identifies the post-path of β_3 as β_7 . Recall, that β_7 is also a candidate for α_3 . Therefore, β_4 merges with β_7 , forming $\beta_m = (\beta_4 \curlyvee \beta_7)$ at step 15 of Algorithm 5. This process continues extending non-equivalent paths until another valid candidate path is found. Now, $r_{\alpha_e} = r_{\beta_m}$ and $\alpha_e \simeq \beta_m$. Therefore, place p_7 of N_0 corresponds to places p'_7 and p'_9 of N_1 which is ensure by the steps 10-14.

Using the same approach, the path α_5 is equivalent to the merged path $\beta_6 \curlyvee \beta_9$ and α_6 is equivalent to the merged path $\beta_5 \curlyvee \beta_8$. With this informal explanation, we now formally define path merging.

Definition 11 (Merge path). *A path α is said to be a Merge path, obtained by merging a set $Q_P = \{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_k\}$ of parallelizable paths [2], if there exists a*

common transition t such that $t \in {}^\circ(\alpha_i)$ for all i , $1 \leq i \leq k$. The path α is denoted as $(\alpha_1 \curlywedge \dots \curlywedge \alpha_k)$. The set of pre-places of α is equal to the union of the pre-places of the paths $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_k$, i.e., ${}^\circ\alpha = \bigcup_{i=1}^k {}^\circ\alpha_i$.

5. (*One-to-one equivalence*): The step 9 of Algorithm 1 asserts that the path α_7 of N_0 are equivalent to β_{11} because their data transformations and execution conditions are equivalent. Since `WasteBin1` is uncommon in β_{10} , it is dropped, after which step 9 also asserts that α_8 is equivalent to β_{10} .

6. (*Non-equivalence*): The path β_{12} has no equivalent path in N_0 , and its execution condition contains the uncommon variable S , causing $(R_\alpha \neg \simeq R_\beta)$. Therefore, the path β_{12} is put in Π'_1 in step 25 of Algorithm 1.

7. (*Termination*): Finally, the method identifies that the non-equivalent path sets of N_1 are not empty in step 30 and accordingly declares that $N_0 \sqsubseteq N_1$ (step 32), i.e., the Petri net N_0 is contained in N_1 .

Correctness and Complexity: The containment checker (Algorithm 1 is iterative over a set of finite paths. At each iteration, the number of paths to be compared is reduced. Therefore, its termination is guaranteed. All the functions which are called by the Algorithm 1 are also terminated. The worst-case time complexity of the containment checking algorithm is exponential because Algorithm 1 invokes the WFF constructor [8] at steps 9, 15, 17, 20, and 21. This constructor checks the equivalence between two expressions, a process that can be exponential in the worst case. The theorem for the soundness of Algorithm 1 is given below.

Theorem 2. *If the function `ContainmentChecker` (Algorithm 1) reaches step 31 and (a) returns $\Pi_{n,0} = \emptyset$, then $N_0 \sqsubseteq N_1$.*

The detailed proof is given in the Appendix.

6 Experimental Results

We tested the tool on the open-source OSCAT library ⁵. The OSCAT library comprises 1,000 applications, organized into 55 clusters based on their complexity. From this library, we selected 80 applications, each of which belongs to at least one of the 55 clusters. These 80 applications were then categorized into four classes, classified on their Lines of Code (LOC) and complexity. The control programs are generally contained within 200 LOC.

Type	Description
Basic	Average 20 lines of program with one loop and two <code>IF THEN ELSE</code> .
Simple	Avg. 40 lines of program with one level nested loop and three <code>IF THEN ELSE</code> .
Medium	Average 60 lines with two level nested loops and there data independent loops.
Complex	Average 90 lines with two or more data independent loops and two or more level nested <code>IF THEN ELSE</code> .

Table 1. Description of various types of benchmarks from OSCAT library

⁵ http://www.oscat.de/images/OSCATBasic/oscat_basic333-en.pdf

6.1 Benchmark Preparation

Table 1 provides an overview of the applications considered for our experimental study. We have considered 80 applications from the OSCAT library and divided them into four classes based on their complexity.

Next, for each of the SFC programs in Table 1, we have taken their upgraded versions from the OSCAT library. These upgradations are essentially the addition of sensors and actuators in the system, as well as some code improvement rules such as loop parallelization, thread-level parallelism, and code motion across the loop, to name a few.

6.2 Experimental Evaluation

We used only a single core of a 2.0GHz Intel[®] Core[™]2 machine to run these benchmarks. For both cases, we have performed the following steps systematically.

Tool Verification: We feed the original and the upgraded version of each benchmark as inputs to our tool. We evaluate the tool’s performance when the original program is contained to the upgraded program and when the upgrade is faulty (i.e., the upgraded version does not retain the original functionality).

Performance: In Table 2, we report the average number of paths for both Petri net models as well as average containment checking time. The 4th column of Table 2 depicts whether the containment checker performed path merging (PM) to establish the containment between two models. As explained in Sec 5, the containment checker may have to perform path merging in the case of either loop distribution followed or thread-level parallelism or both. Here we observe that path merging takes place in the **Medium** and **Complex** classes of OSCAT benchmarks. The 5th column of Table 2 depicts whether the containment checker performed path extension (PE) to establish the containment between two models. As explained in Sec 5, the containment checker may have to perform path extension in the case of either non-uniform code transformations. Here, we observe that path extension occurs in the **Simple** and **Complex** classes of OSCAT benchmarks.

Comparison: We compare our approach with a popular state-of-the-art tool **verifAPS**⁶ [5], which is often used for software upgrades. This tool takes two SFCs as input and translates them into a subset of Structured Text. During this process, it eliminates all uncommon variables from the two SFCs, similar to our approach. Then they are converted to SMV models [14] and these two SMV models are verified for equivalence using NuXMV⁷. Unlike ours, **verifAPS** employs an inductive inference-based technique [15]. We compare our results with those produced by **verifAPS** in the last column of Table 2. Our method

⁶ <https://formal.kastel.kit.edu/~weigl/verifaps/stvs/>

⁷ <https://nuxmv.fbk.eu/>

is approximately $\approx 4X$ faster than `verifAPS` because it translates the SFC to a Petri net in a syntactic way and uses path-based containment checking. This approach eliminates the need for invariant computation at each state, unlike `verifAPS`, which translates the SFC into two intermediate representations and computes the invariant during equivalence checking.

6.3 Fault Injection

In order to experimentally evaluate the performance of the tool in the presence of faulty code upgradation, we inject some errors in the SFC and observe the time it takes to detect these errors during the containment checking process. We have introduced the following types of (both control level and thread level) erroneous code upgradation.

1. **Type 1:** non-uniform boosting up assignment statement motions from one branch of step to the step preceding it, which introduces false-data dependencies; this has been injected into the `Medium` and `Simple` benchmarks.
2. **Type 2:** non-uniform duplicating down assignment statement motions from the step where bifurcation takes place to one branch that removes data dependency in the other branch; this has been injected in the `Complex` and `Basic` benchmarks.
3. **Type 3:** data-locality transformations which introduce false data-locality in the body of the loop in `Medium` and `Complex` benchmarks.

Benchmarks	# Paths from Original SFC	# Paths from Upgraded SFC	PM	PE	Time (Sec)	<code>verifAPS</code> Time (sec)
Basic	7	7	NO	NO	1.43	5.45
Simple	9	9	NO	YES	1.54	7.2
Medium	9	12	YES	NO	3.01	11.23
Complex	17	19	YES	YES	6.12	28.3

Table 2. Containment checking results

Types	Benchmarks	Time (Sec)	1-BisimDegree	<code>verifAPS</code> Time (Sec)
Type 1	Medium	12.12	20 %	55.4
	Simple	1.27	10%	12.2
Type 2	Complex	14.11	22%	–
	Basic	1.23	8%	–
Type 3	Medium	2.43	14%	10.43
	Complex	5.32	21%	24.31

Table 3. Non-Equivalence checking times for faulty upgradation

The third column of Table 3 shows the non-equivalence detection time in seconds. For OSCAT benchmarks, we have taken the average non-equivalence checking time for the “no” answer. The fourth column computes the fraction of non-equivalent paths for the two programs, expressed as $1 - \text{BisimDegree}$ (Definition 12). Here, the non-equivalence arises due to the injection of faults during upgradation.

Definition 12 (Degree of Bisimilarity). *The Degree of Bisimilarity (BisimDegree) between two models N_0 and N_1 comprising path sets Π_0 and Π_1 respectively, is defined as $BisimDegree = \frac{|\Pi_0 \cap \Pi_1|}{|\Pi_0 \cup \Pi_1|}$ where $\Pi_0 \cap \Pi_1$ comprises all pairs $\alpha \in \Pi_0, \beta \in \Pi_1$, such that $\alpha \simeq \beta$, as defined in Definition 10.*

The last column depicts the non-equivalence detection time for `verifAPS` tool. Here we observe that the tool `verifAPS` takes more time to detect equivalence than our tool because of checking the invariant in each state of the translated ST code from SFC. It is also to be noted that the **Type 2** error cannot be detected by `verifAPS` tool.

Fig. 6. Limitations of our method

7 Discussion

In light of the experimental results, we highlight several usage scenarios of the tool and mention a few limitations.

7.1 Utility of the Tool

Efficiency in Regression Testing: Since our tool relies on symbolic containment checking, an “yes” answer from the tool (the original code is contained in the upgraded code) completely eliminates any further testing. However, the tool is not *complete*, therefore, it is always possible that the tool falsely declares two containment programs as *non-equivalent*. In such a case, the testing team needs to manually investigate if the upgradation process is indeed correct. Thus, the tool offers an assistive approach as it does not completely automate verification. An objective evaluation of effort reduction requires rigorous field testing, which will be taken up by the engineering team. Currently, we have conducted a

controlled field trial with a selected set of PLC experts. A ballpark comparison revealed that our verification approach is $\approx 10X$ faster than manual testing; an SFC testing generally takes 3 to 5 minutes by a domain expert in a testing environment. The experts has reported an effort reduction of the order of 60-80% in most cases. Furthermore, we have observed that our tool has been able to successfully detect containment of nearly 90% of software upgradation use cases.

Upgradation Assistance: The Developer Assistance component shown in Figure 1 currently generates an elaborate report of equivalent and non-equivalent paths for the old and upgraded versions with the corresponding source code. This can be easily extended, where the tool is a plugin to a popular IDE (VS-Code, Eclipse) and can provide real-time feedback by highlighting the portion of the source codes that are found to be non-equivalent. The user can then decide to accept or reject the suggestion given by the tool.

Noteworthy Capabilities: Our tool can handle various syntactic upgradations, including upgradation of data type, control structures, and more. Additionally, it captures several types of semantic-level upgradation, such as uniform and non-uniform code movement, loop-invariant code translation, code motion across loops, and thread-level parallelizing transformations.

7.2 Limitations

We illustrate an important limitation by manually creating a new version of the SFC (Figure 6(a)) that is functionally equivalent to the original SFC code as shown in Figure 3(a), but non-bisimilar. We took the help of the open source SFC expert to ensure that this new version of the SFC, the original SFC (Figure 3(a)), and the upgraded SFC (Figure 3(b)) are all functionally equivalent. Figure 6(b) is the corresponding Petri net model generated by the proposed tool. Our method cannot establish containment between the Petri net in Figure 6(b)) and the Petri net model of the SFC code in Figure 4(c) because they are non-bisimilar.

The SFC code Figure 3(a) has two parallel loop containing two independent operations. The variable *Fixer* determines how many times the loop will run. In the hand-crafted SFC in Figure 6(a), the operations (multiplying *a* and dividing *b*) are split into two separate loops for parallelism, and the loop is also split in half. The first loop runs for *Fixer*/2 iterations, and then the second loop continues until the variable reaches *Fixer*. Since the loop iterations differ between SFC in Figure 3(a) and the hand-crafted SFC in Figure 6(a), the programs are considered non-bisimilar. In Figure 6(a), the red boundaries show the non-bisimilar portions. The containment checker can not find paths in Figure 4(c) that are equivalent to the paths $\gamma_4, \dots \gamma_{16}$ in the Petri net shown in Figure 6(b). In this example, the percentage of non-bisimilarity $(1 - \text{BisimDegree}) = 72.2\%$.

Another type of non-bisimilarity can arise if arithmetic expressions are modified without changing the functionality. For instance, if the multiplication operation is replaced with addition and shift operations, our current version of the tool will fail to establish their equivalence. The method is not scalable at all.

8 Related Work

Verifying safety-critical systems has gained prominence since 2000 and has emerged as a serious concern across various industries. Numerous literature sources [16–28] have recognized this problem and reported various verification schemes. A detailed survey [29] reported different verification approaches for IEC 61131-3 languages. Simon et al. [30] introduced test case generation for PLC software using a model checker that iteratively created program traces, trying to increase coverage metrics.

There have been two distinct approaches for verifying SFCs: model checking and theorem proving, both stemming from the SFC’s ancestor standard Grafset [31]. The model-checking approach translates SFCs into transition systems utilizing various models such as timed automata, hybrid automata, or state machines. Several property verification techniques for PLC programs are reported in [32–38, 27, 5, 39, 22, 21, 40, 41]. These approaches primarily focus on verifying safety or liveness properties of subsets of IEC 61131-3 languages or language features. On the other hand, the theorem-proving method attempts to certify the properties of SFC-based system specifications, as reported in several studies [42–45].

Unlike these approaches, our focus is on the behavioural verification of the upgradation process, where our tool checks whether the original code is behaviourally contained to the upgraded code. The tool `verifAPS` reported in [5] describes an inductive inference-based approach for checking equivalence between two versions of SFCs. Behavioural verification and its applications have been well studied; several techniques for code-level verification are reported in [11, 10, 12, 46, 15, 47–50, 1, 51–56]. A comprehensive and exhaustive set of benchmarks for various behavioural verification techniques is reported in [57]. In addition, several model-based behavioural verification methods are discussed in [58–63]. However, to the best of our knowledge, there has been *no reported work* on path based behavioral verification in the context of *software upgradation of PLC programs*.

9 Conclusion

In this work, we proposed a formally grounded verification framework to validate whether behavioral correctness is preserved during software upgrades of PLC software. Our approach introduces a novel technique that checks for behavioral containment through symbolic path equivalence of two Petri net models. Experimental evaluation on a diverse suite of benchmarks from the OSCAT library demonstrates the scalability and efficacy of our tool, with significant performance gains over the state-of-the-art *verifAPS* system. Our method is reliable, it does not give any false positive results. Our approach is language-agnostic; it can be extended to verify equivalence between any two control programs, as long as they are mapped to Petri nets.

An important limitation of our method is, its inability to handle hierarchical SFC as well as non-bisimilar SFCs. This is due to the restriction of traversing each loop exactly once. Furthermore, our method cannot accommodate timing

behaviour (like TON construct), writable shared variables, and only operates on integer and boolean type variables. Overcoming these limitations will be key focus areas for our *future work*.

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Appendix

Algorithm 2: PathConstructor(N)

Input: A Petri net model N
Output: Set of paths Q created from the set of cut-points in N

- 1: $M_h \leftarrow P_{M_0}$; /* initialized to initial marked places in N^* /
- $Q \leftarrow \emptyset$;
- $T_{sh} \langle \rangle$; // Sequence of sets of transitions
- $tick \leftarrow 0$;
- 2: $\mathcal{T} \leftarrow \text{computeAllConcurTrans} (M_h, N)$; /* returns all possible set of sets of concurrent mutually exclusive transitions to M_h */
- 3: **for all** $T_e \in \mathcal{T}$ **do**
- 4: $Q \leftarrow Q \cup \text{getPathsForexecutionCutPt} (M_h, T_e, T_{sh}, tick, N)$
- 5: **end for**
- 6: **return** Q ;

Algorithm 3: getPathsForexecutionCutPt($M_h, T_e, T_{sh}, tick, N$)

Input: M_h is a marking, T_e is a set of enabled maximally parallelizable transitions and N is the Petri net model. T_{sh} : sequence of sets of transitions.
 tick: Tick value

Output: Set of paths Q

- 1: $C_d \leftarrow \emptyset$; // execution cut-point list
- 2: **if** $T_e == \emptyset$ **then**
- 3: **return** Q ;
- 4: **end if**
- 5: $\forall t \in T_e$, mark t
- 6: $M_{new} \leftarrow T_e^\circ$; /* post-places of T_e acquire tokens */
- 7: $T_{sh} = T_{sh}.T_e$
- 8: $M_h \leftarrow (M_h - \circ T_e) \cup M_{new}$;
- 9: $\forall t \in T_e$, TickStamp[t] \leftarrow tick;
- 10: **if** (\exists back-edge leading to some $p \in M_h$) or ($|T_e^\circ| > |T_e|$) **then**
- 11: $C_d \leftarrow C_d \cup M_h$
- 12: **for all** $p' \in M_h$ **do**
- 13: $\alpha \leftarrow \text{constOnePath} (\{p'\}, T_{sh}, N)$; // Traverse backward from $\{p'\}$ along T_{sh} to construct a path up to some cut-points
- 14: $Q = Q \cup \{\alpha\}$
- 15: **end for**
- 16: **end if**
- 17: $\mathcal{T} \leftarrow \text{computeAllConcurTrans} (M_h, N)$;
- 18: **if** ($\mathcal{T} = \emptyset$) and ($M_h \neq \emptyset$) **then**
- 19: Report as invalid PRES+ Model
- 20: **else**
- 21: **for all** $T_e \in \mathcal{T}$ **do**
- 22: $T_e \leftarrow T_e - \{\text{marked transitions of } T_e\}$
- 23: $Q \leftarrow Q \cup \text{getPathsForexecutionCutPt} (M_h, T_e, T_{sh}, tick + 1, N)$
- 24: **end for**
- 25: **end if**
- 26: **return** Q ;

Algorithm 4: prepareForExtension($\gamma, \Pi', \Pi_n, \eta_t, E$)

Input: 1. γ : a path whose extension is sought. 2. Π' : a set of paths remaining from the original path cover. 3. Π_n : a set of non-equivalent paths 4. η_t : the set of corresponding transitions pairs. 5. E : pair of equivalent paths of N_0 and N_1 .

Output: Modified Π' remaining from the original path and modified Π

- 1: $\Pi' = \Pi' - \{\gamma\}$; /* γ has to be extended */
- 2: $\Gamma_E^+ = \mathbf{findPostPaths}(\gamma, \Pi')$;
/* Computes post-paths of γ through which γ can be extended. Such paths include those which emanate from the post-place γ° (under different guards) or those which emanate from the post-places of the last transition of γ . */
- 3: **for** each $\gamma' \in \Gamma_E^+$ **do**
- 4: $\chi_\gamma = \mathbf{findSetOfSetsOfPrePaths}(\gamma, \gamma', \Pi', E)$;
/* Computes all the pre-paths of γ' other than γ . Some of these may not execute in parallel (with γ). For example, let $\{\gamma, \gamma_1, \gamma_2, \gamma_3\}$ be three pre-paths of γ' ; assume that γ_2 and γ_3 have an identical post-place. Hence, γ_2 and γ_3 cannot execute in parallel because the models are one(k)-safe. So the pre-paths (including γ) will be $\{\{\gamma, \gamma_1, \gamma_2\}, \{\gamma, \gamma_1, \gamma_3\}\}$. */
- 5: $\Pi' = \Pi' - \{\gamma'\}$;
- 6: **for all** $\Gamma_P \in \chi_\gamma$ **do**
- 7: $(\Gamma'_P, \Pi_n) = \mathbf{trimPrePaths}(\gamma, \Gamma_P, \Pi', \eta_t, E)$; /* Γ_P is trimmed of the members (other than γ) which are found to have equivalence (without any extension) with some path in the other model. If it is detected that such a path may have to be extended before its equivalence is found, then no action is initiated because they are already under consideration for extension. However, if it is found that the path does not need any further consideration (such as extension), it is put in the set Π_n which may have no equivalent path in the other model. The set is not used for extension. */
- 8: **if** $(\Gamma'_P \neq \emptyset)$ **then**
- 9: $\gamma_e = \mathbf{extend}(\gamma, \Gamma'_P, \gamma')$; /* Constructs an extended path γ_e of the form $\Gamma_P.\gamma'$. The function computes those pre-places of γ' paths leading to which have been found to have equivalent paths and hence do not occur in Γ_P . Then the function computes the pre-places of γ_e . In the next two steps, the function obtains the post-places of γ_e as those of γ' and the last transition of γ_e as that of γ' . After that, by method of substitution the function computes the condition R_{γ_e} of execution and the data transformation r_{γ_e} along the extended path γ_e . Removes all uncommon variables from path. Finally, it returns the extended path γ_e */
- 10: $\Pi' = (\Pi' - \Gamma_P) \cup \{\gamma_e\}$;
- 11: **end if**
- 12: **end for**
- 13: **end for**
- 14: **return** Π' ;

Algorithm 5: prepareForMerging(Γ)

Input: Γ : A candidate set of paths such that $\Gamma \subseteq \Pi_0$ or $\Gamma \subseteq \Pi_1$ **Output:** Returns a merged path γ_m formed from converging paths (if found), or \emptyset otherwise.

```

1:  $\mathcal{C} \leftarrow \Gamma$ ; /* Candidate set for merging from one model only */
2:  $\mathcal{P} \leftarrow \emptyset$ ;
3: for all path  $\gamma \in \mathcal{C}$  do
4:    $\text{PrePaths} \leftarrow \circ\gamma$ ;
5:    $\mathcal{P} \leftarrow \mathcal{P} \cup \text{PrePaths}$ ;
6: end for
7:  $\mathcal{S} \leftarrow \text{allNontrivialSubsets}(\mathcal{P})$ ; /* All subsets of size  $\geq 2$  */
8: for all subset  $\mathcal{G} \in \mathcal{S}$  do
9:    $\mathcal{T}_{last} \leftarrow \{last(\gamma) \mid \gamma \in \mathcal{G}\}$ ;
10:  if  $\mathcal{T}_{last}$  is singleton then
11:    Let  $\tau$  be the unique transition in  $\mathcal{T}_{last}$ ;
12:    Let  $\tau^\circ$  be the post-places of  $\tau$ ;
13:    Let  $P_G$  be the set of starting places of all paths in  $\mathcal{G}$ ;
14:    if  $\exists t \mid P_G \subseteq t^\circ$  then
15:       $\gamma_m \leftarrow \text{mergePaths}(\mathcal{G}, \tau)$ ; /* This condition implies that all paths in  $\mathcal{G}$ 
        originate from the transition  $t$ , and their execution conditions are same. */
16:      return  $\gamma_m$ ;
17:    end if
18:  end if
19: end for
20: if  $\mathcal{P} = \mathcal{C}$  then
21:  return  $\emptyset$ ; /* No further expansion, no merge point */
22: end if

```

Theorem 1: A Petri net model N_0 is contained in another Petri net model N_1 , denoted as $N_0 \sqsubseteq N_1$, for all finite path cover $\Pi_0 = \{\alpha_0, \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_l\}$ of N_0 for which there exists a set $\Pi_1 = \{\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_l\}$ of paths of N_1 such that for all $i, 0 \leq i \leq l$, (i) $\alpha_i \simeq \beta_i$, (ii) the places in ${}^\circ\alpha_i$ have correspondence with those in ${}^\circ\beta_i$ and (iii) the places in α_i° have correspondence with those in β_i° .

Proof. Consider any computation μ_p for an out-port p of N_0 . It is required to prove that for the out-port $p' = f_{out}(p)$ of N_1 , there exists a computation $\mu_{p'} \simeq \mu_p$. Let $\mu_p = \langle T_1, T_2, \dots, T_i, \dots, T_l \rangle$ where, ${}^\circ T_1 = P_{M_0}$, $p \in T_l^\circ$ and for all $i, 1 \leq i \leq l$, if $T_i^\circ \subseteq P_{M_i}$, for some marking M_i and $T_{i+1}^\circ \subseteq P_{M_{i+1}}$, for some marking M_{i+1} , then $M_{i+1} = M_i^+$. Since Π_0 is a path cover of N_0 , μ_p can be captured as a concatenation $(\alpha_1^{(1)} \parallel \alpha_2^{(1)} \parallel \dots \parallel \alpha_{n_1}^{(1)}).(\alpha_1^{(2)} \parallel \alpha_2^{(2)} \parallel \dots \parallel \alpha_{n_2}^{(2)}) \dots (\alpha_1^{(l)}) = \mu_p^c$, say, of parallelisable paths of Π_0 such that $\mu_p \simeq \mu_p^c$. (Note that the last member in the concatenated sequence must be a single path because the last set T_l in μ_p is a singleton because of synchronizing transition.)

From μ_p^c let us construct a concatenated sequence $\mu_{p'}^c = (\beta_1^{(1)} \parallel \beta_2^{(1)} \parallel \dots \parallel \beta_{n_1}^{(1)}).(\beta_1^{(2)} \parallel \beta_2^{(2)} \parallel \dots \parallel \beta_{n_2}^{(2)}) \dots (\beta_1^{(l)})$ of parallelisable paths of N_1 such that for all $i, 1 \leq i \leq l$, for all $j, 1 \leq j \leq n_i$, $\alpha_j^{(i)} \simeq \beta_j^{(i)}$ with any place in ${}^\circ(\alpha_j^{(i)})$ having a correspondence with some place in ${}^\circ(\beta_j^{(i)})$ and any place in $(\alpha_j^{(i)})^\circ$ having a correspondence with some place in $(\beta_j^{(i)})^\circ$. From the premise of the theorem, such paths exist; also, $\mu_p^c \simeq \mu_{p'}^c$.

We now prove that $\mu_{p'}^c$ is indeed a computation. Consider the i^{th} group $(\beta_1^{(i)} \parallel \beta_2^{(i)} \parallel \dots \parallel \beta_{n_i}^{(i)})$ of $\mu_{p'}^c$. For any $j, 1 \leq j \leq n_i$, let the j^{th} path $\beta_j^{(i)}$ in the i^{th} group be the sequence $\langle T_{1,j}^{(i)}, T_{2,j}^{(i)}, \dots, T_{l_j,j}^{(i)} \rangle$ of parallelisable transitions. For all $k, 1 \leq k \leq \max_{j=1}^{n_i}(l_j)$, we combine all the k^{th} transitions of all the paths in the i^{th} group through the union operation to form a single set of parallelisable transitions $T_k^{(i)} = \bigcup_{j=1}^{n_i} T_{k,j}^{(i)}$. Obviously, the paths in the i^{th} group can be of varying lengths and those having lengths less than k will not contribute to the set T_k . Let the maximum length of the paths occurring in the i^{th} group be m_i . Then the above step of combining the transition sets of the paths group-wise results in a sequence of parallelisable transitions $\mu_{p'}^c = \langle T_1^{(1)}, T_2^{(1)}, \dots, T_{m_1}^{(1)}, T_1^{(2)}, \dots, T_{m_2}^{(2)}, \dots, T_1^{(l)}, \dots, T_{m_l}^{(l)} \rangle$. We show that $\mu_{p'}^c$ is a computation of the out-port p' of N_1 as per definition of computation. What remains to be proved is that for any two consecutive transition sets T, T^+ in $\mu_{p'}^c$, if $(T^+)^\circ \subseteq P'_{M_{i+1}}$ and $(T)^\circ \subseteq P'_{M_i}$, then $M'_{i+1} = M_i'^+$, i.e., $P'_{M_{i+1}} = P'_{M_i}^+$. Recall that

$$P'_{M_i^+} = \{p \mid p \in T^\circ \text{ and } t \in T'_{M_i}\} \cup \{p \mid p \in P'_{M_i} \text{ and } p \notin {}^\circ T'_{M_i}\} \dots (1)$$

Note that $T'^+ = T'_{M_i}$, the set of enabled transitions for the marking M_i' . We give the proof of $P'_{M_{i+1}} \subseteq P'_{M_i^+}$; the proof of $P'_{M_i^+} \subseteq P'_{M_{i+1}}$ follows identically. Now, consider any $p \in P'_{M_{i+1}}$. Either $p' \in (T'^+)^\circ$ or $p' \notin (T'^+)^\circ$.

- *Case 1:* $p' \in (T^+)^{\circ} \Rightarrow p \in t$, for some $t' \in T'^+ = T'_{M_i} \Rightarrow p' \in P'_{M_i^+}$ because $p' \in$ the first subset in the Definition 3 of $P'_{M_i^+}$.
- *Case 2:* $p \notin (T^+)^{\circ}$: In this case, $p' \in P'_{M_{i+1}} \Rightarrow p \in P'_{M_i}$ and $p' \notin {}^{\circ}t'$, for any $t' \in T'^+ = T'_{M_i} \Rightarrow p \in P'_{M_i}$ and $p' \notin {}^{\circ}T'_{M_i} \Rightarrow p' \in P'_{M_i^+}$ because it belongs to the second subset in the Definition 3 of $P'_{M_i^+}$.

Theorem 2: If the function `ContainmentChecker` (Algorithm 1) reaches step 31 and (a) returns $\Pi_{n,0}$

Proof. Let Π_0 gives a path cover of N_0 . Hence, for any out-port p of N_0 , any computation μ_p can be represented as a concatenation, $Q_0.Q_1 \dots Q_l$ say, of sets of parallel paths, such that $p \in Q_l^{\circ}$, ${}^{\circ}Q_0 = P_{M_0}$, Q_l is a singleton $\{\alpha_l\}$, say, and Q_i contains only paths from Π_0 , $0 \leq i \leq l$. Whenever a path α is introduced in Π_0 (only in step 11 of Algorithm 1) an entry $\langle \alpha, \beta \rangle$ is introduced in E (with $\alpha \simeq \beta$). Hence, for any path $\alpha \in Q_i$ for some i , there exists a path β of N_1 such that $\langle \alpha, \beta \rangle \in E$. Hence, we can construct a concatenation, $C'_{p'}$ say, of parallel paths of N_1 such that $C'_{p'} = Q'_0.Q'_1 \dots Q'_l$, where $Q'_i = \{\beta \mid \langle \alpha, \beta \rangle \in E \text{ and } \alpha \in Q_i\}$. We show that

1. *Case 1:* $C'_{p'}$ is a computation of $f_{out}(p)$ in N_1 .
2. *Case 2:* $C'_{p'} \simeq_c \mu_p$.

Proof of Case 1: $C'_{p'}$ is alternatively rewritten as a sequence of sets of places, namely, $\langle {}^{\circ}Q'_0, {}^{\circ}Q'_1, \dots, {}^{\circ}Q'_i, {}^{\circ}Q'_{i+1}, \dots, {}^{\circ}Q'_l, Q'_l{}^{\circ} \rangle$. It is required to prove (a) $Q'_1 \subseteq P'_{M_0}$, (b) $f_{out}(p) \in Q'_l{}^{\circ}$, (c) $Q'_{i+1}{}^{\circ} = (Q'_i{}^{\circ})^+$, $0 \leq i \leq l$.

Proof of (a): A pair $\langle \alpha, \beta \rangle$ of paths is put in E by the function `ContainmentChecker` (Algorithm 1) (step 11) if they are ascertained to be equivalent; the latter will examine their equivalence only if they are found to satisfy the property ${}^{\circ}\alpha = P_{M_0} \Rightarrow {}^{\circ}\beta = P'_{M_0}$ and ${}^{\circ}\beta = \phi^1({}^{\circ}\alpha)$ by the function `SelectPathForCheckingEquivalence`. Hence, ${}^{\circ}Q_0 = P_{M_0} \Rightarrow {}^{\circ}Q'_0 = P'_{M_0}$ and ${}^{\circ}Q'_0 = f_{in}({}^{\circ}Q_0)$.

Proof of (b): By construction of $C'_{p'}$ from μ_p , $Q'_l = \{\beta_l\}$ is a singleton and if $Q_l = \{\alpha_l\}$, then $\langle \alpha_l, \beta_l \rangle \in E$ (by construction of $C'_{p'}$). Again, by similar reasoning as in the proof of (a), we find that the function `SelectPathForCheckingEquivalence` that $\alpha_l{}^{\circ} \in outP_0 \Rightarrow \beta_l{}^{\circ} (= Q'_l{}^{\circ}) \in f_{out}(\alpha_l{}^{\circ}) = f_{out}(p)$.

Proof of (c): Given $C'_{p'} = Q'_0.Q'_1 \dots Q'_l$. We construct the corresponding sequence of subsets of place marking $\varrho = \langle P_{M_0}, P_{M_1}, \dots, P_{M_l}, P_{M_{l+1}} \rangle$ such that

$$P_{M_0} = {}^{\circ}C'_{p'} \quad (1)$$

$$\forall i, 0 \leq i \leq l, P_{M_{i+1}} = \{p \mid p \in Q'_i{}^{\circ} \cap {}^{\circ}Q'_{i+1}\} \dots (a) \quad (2)$$

$$\cup \{p \mid p \in Q'_i{}^{\circ} - {}^{\circ}Q'_{i+1}\} \dots (b) \quad (3)$$

$$\cup \{p \mid p \in P_{M_i} - {}^{\circ}Q'_i\} \dots (c) \quad (4)$$

$$P_{M_i} = Q_i^{\circ} \quad (5)$$

Now, $C'_{p'}$ is a computation of N_1 if ϱ is a computation of p' ; hence it is required to prove $(I)P_{M_0} \subseteq inP_1$, $(II)P_{M_{i+1}} = \{p'\}$, $(III)P_{M_{i+1}} = P_{M_i}^+$, $0 \leq i < l$.

Proof of (I) and (II): (I) and (II) are already proved in part (a) and part (b).

Proof of (III): If $p \in P_{M_{i+1}}$ by clause 2(a) or 2(b), then $p \in Q_i^{\circ}$, where $Q_i^{\circ} = T_{M_i}$, the set of enabled transitions from marking M_i . If $p \in P_{M_{i+1}}$ by clause 2(c), then $p \in P_{M_i}$ and $p \notin Q_i^{\circ} \Rightarrow p \in P_{M_i}$ and $p \notin T_{M_i}$. Thus, the set $P_{M_{i+1}}$ of places satisfies the Definition 3) of place successor marking. Hence $P_{M_{i+1}} = P_{M_i}^+$.

Proof of Case 2: In $C'_{p'}$, $\forall p_1 \in Q_i^{\circ}$, $0 \leq i \leq l$, there exists a concatenated path γ_{p_1} of the form $Q_0^{Q_1^{p_1}}.Q_1^{Q_1^{p_1}} \dots .Q_i^{Q_1^{p_1}}$ such that $(Q_i^{p_1})^{\circ} = \{p_1\}$ (by Definition of concatenated paths[2]). The path γ_{p_1} has a condition of execution $R_{\gamma_{p_1}}^{Q_0^{\circ}}(\phi(\circ\gamma_{p_1}))$, the data transformation $r_{\gamma_{p_1}}^{Q_0^{\circ}}(\phi(\circ\gamma_{p_1}))$ and the tick-Stamp $\text{TickStamp}(\text{last}(\gamma_{p_1}^{Q_0^{\circ}}))$. Similarly, in $\mu_{0,p}$, $\forall p_0 \in Q_i^{\circ}$, $0 \leq i \leq l$, we can have a path γ_{p_0} . So, to prove that $C'_{p'} \simeq \mu_p$, we have to show that $\forall i, 0 \leq i \leq l$, $\forall p_1 \in Q_i^{\circ}$, $\exists p_0 \in Q_i^{\circ}$ such that $\langle p_0, p_1 \rangle \in \eta_p$, $R_{\gamma_{p_1}}^{Q_0^{\circ}}(\phi(\circ\gamma_{p_1})) \equiv R_{\gamma_{p_0}}^{Q_0^{\circ}}(\phi(\circ\gamma_{p_0}))$, $r_{\gamma_{p_1}}^{Q_0^{\circ}}(\phi(\circ\gamma_{p_1})) = r_{\gamma_{p_0}}^{Q_0^{\circ}}(\phi(\circ\gamma_{p_0}))$ and $\text{TickStamp}(\text{last}(\gamma_{p_1}^{Q_0^{\circ}})) = \text{TickStamp}(\text{last}(\gamma_{p_0}^{Q_0^{\circ}}))$ by induction on i .

Basis ($i = 0$): $\forall p_1 \in Q_0^{\circ}$, $\exists \beta \in Q_0^{\circ}$, such that $\beta^{\circ} = \{p_1\}$. So, $\gamma_{p_1} = \beta$. By construction of $C'_{p'}$ from μ_p , $\exists \alpha, \langle \alpha, \beta \rangle \in E$ and $\alpha \in Q_0$. Let $\{p_0\}$ be α° ; so $\alpha = \gamma_{p_0}$. As $\langle \alpha, \beta \rangle \in E$, $R_{\alpha}(\phi(\circ\alpha)) \equiv R_{\beta}(\phi(\circ\beta))$, $r_{\alpha}(\phi(\circ\alpha)) = r_{\beta}(\phi(\circ\beta))$ and $\text{TickStamp}(\text{last}(\alpha)) = \text{TickStamp}(\text{last}(\beta))$ (ensured by Algorithm 1). Therefore, $R_{\gamma_{p_1}}^{Q_0^{\circ}}(\phi(\circ\gamma_{p_1})) \equiv R_{\gamma_{p_0}}^{Q_0^{\circ}}(\phi(\circ\gamma_{p_0}))$, $r_{\gamma_{p_1}}^{Q_0^{\circ}}(\phi(\circ\gamma_{p_1})) = r_{\gamma_{p_0}}^{Q_0^{\circ}}(\phi(\circ\gamma_{p_0}))$ and $\text{TickStamp}(\text{last}(\gamma_{p_1}^{Q_0^{\circ}})) = \text{TickStamp}(\text{last}(\gamma_{p_0}^{Q_0^{\circ}}))$; also, $\langle p_0, p_1 \rangle \in \eta_p$ as ensured by Algorithm 1.

Induction Hypothesis: Let $\forall i, 0 \leq i \leq k < l$, $\forall p_1 \in Q_i^{\circ}$, $\exists p_0 \in Q_i^{\circ}$ such that the properties

$$\begin{aligned} R_{\gamma_{p_1}}^{Q_0^{\circ}}(\phi(\circ\gamma_{p_1})) &\equiv R_{\gamma_{p_0}}^{Q_0^{\circ}}(\phi(\circ\gamma_{p_0})), \\ r_{\gamma_{p_1}}^{Q_0^{\circ}}(\phi(\circ\gamma_{p_1})) &= r_{\gamma_{p_0}}^{Q_0^{\circ}}(\phi(\circ\gamma_{p_0})), \\ \text{TickStamp}(\text{last}(\gamma_{p_1}^{Q_0^{\circ}})) &= \text{TickStamp}(\text{last}(\gamma_{p_0}^{Q_0^{\circ}})) \\ \text{and } \langle p_0, p_1 \rangle &\in \eta_p \text{ hold.} \end{aligned}$$

Induction Step: Required to prove that $\forall p_1 \in Q_{k+1}^{\circ}$, $\exists p_0 \in Q_{k+1}^{\circ}$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} R_{\gamma_{p_1}}^{Q_0^{\circ}}(\phi(\circ\gamma_{p_1})) &\equiv R_{\gamma_{p_0}}^{Q_0^{\circ}}(\phi(\circ\gamma_{p_0})), r_{\gamma_{p_1}}^{Q_0^{\circ}}(\phi(\circ\gamma_{p_1})) = \\ r_{\gamma_{p_0}}^{Q_0^{\circ}}(\phi(\circ\gamma_{p_0})), \text{TickStamp}(\text{last}(\gamma_{p_1}^{Q_0^{\circ}})) &= \text{TickStamp}(\text{last}(\gamma_{p_0}^{Q_0^{\circ}})) \text{ and } \langle p_0, p_1 \rangle \in \\ \eta_p. \text{ Let } \gamma_{p_1} &= C_1'' \cdot \beta, \text{ where } \beta^{\circ} = \{p_1\} \text{ and } C_1' \text{ is a set of parallelisable} \\ \text{paths such that } (C_1')^{\circ} &= \circ\beta. \text{ Let } C_1' = \beta_1 || \beta_2 || \dots || \beta_{t_1}. \text{ Now, } \exists \alpha, \langle \alpha, \beta \rangle \in \\ E \text{ (by construction of } C'_{p'} &\text{ from } \mu_p). \text{ Therefore, as ensured by the Algo-} \\ \text{rithm 1 } R_{\alpha}(\phi(\circ\alpha)) &\equiv R_{\beta}(\phi(\circ\beta)), r_{\alpha}(\phi(\circ\alpha)) = r_{\beta}(\phi(\circ\beta)) \text{ and } \langle \alpha^{\circ}, \beta^{\circ} \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

Let p_0 be α° . $\gamma_{p_0} = C'_0 \cdot \alpha$, where C'_0 is a set of parallelisable paths of the form $\alpha_1 || \alpha_2 || \dots || \alpha_{t_1}$ such that $\langle \alpha_i, \beta_i \rangle \in E, 1 \leq i \leq t_1$. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & R_{\gamma_{p_1}}^{Q'_0}(\phi(\circ \gamma_{p_1})) \\
 & \equiv \bigwedge_{i=1}^{t_1} R_{\beta_i}(\phi(\circ \beta_i)) \wedge R_{\beta}(\phi(\circ \beta)) \{ \overline{v_1} / \phi(\circ \beta) \} \\
 & \quad \text{where, } \overline{v_1} = \langle r_{\beta_1}(\phi(\circ \beta_1)), r_{\beta_2}(\phi(\circ \beta_2)), \dots, r_{\beta_{t_1}}(\phi(\circ \beta_{t_1})) \rangle \\
 & \equiv \bigwedge_{i=1}^{t_1} R_{\alpha_i}(\phi(\circ \alpha_i)) \wedge R_{\alpha}(\phi(\circ \alpha)) \{ \overline{v_0} / \phi(\circ \alpha) \} \\
 & \quad \text{where, } \overline{v_0} = \langle r_{\alpha_1}(\phi(\circ \alpha_1)), r_{\alpha_2}(\phi(\circ \alpha_2)), \dots, r_{\alpha_{t_1}}(\phi(\circ \alpha_{t_1})) \rangle; \\
 & \equiv R_{C_{p_0}^{Q'_0}}(\phi(\circ C_{p_1})).
 \end{aligned}$$

Since by induction hypothesis $r_{\alpha_j}(\phi(\circ \alpha_j)) = r_{\beta_j}(\phi(\circ \beta_j))$,
 $\text{TickStamp}(\text{last}(\alpha_j)) = \text{TickStamp}(\text{last}(\beta_j)) \quad 1 \leq j \leq t_1$, and
 $R_{\alpha_i}(\phi(\circ \alpha_i)) \equiv R_{\beta_i}(\phi(\circ \beta_i))$,
 since $R_{\beta}(\phi(\circ \beta)) \equiv R_{\alpha}(\phi(\circ \alpha))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{Similarly, } r_{\gamma_{p_1}}^{Q'_0}(\phi(\circ \gamma_{p_1})) \\
 & = r_{\beta}(\phi(\circ \beta)) \{ \overline{v_1} / \phi(\circ \beta) \} \\
 & = r_{\alpha}(\phi(\circ \alpha)) \{ \overline{v_0} / \phi(\circ \alpha) \} \\
 & \quad \text{since, } \langle \alpha, \beta \rangle \in E \text{ and } \overline{v_1} = \overline{v_0} \text{ by induction hypothesis} \\
 & = r_{C_{p_0}^{Q_{0,0}}}(\phi(\circ C_{p_0})).
 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, $\text{TickStamp}(\text{last}(\gamma_{p_1})) = \text{TickStamp}(\text{last}(\beta)) = \text{TickStamp}(\text{last}(\alpha))$
 since, $\langle \alpha, \beta \rangle \in E$ and $\overline{v_1} = \overline{v_0}$ by induction hypothesis
 $= \text{TickStamp}(\text{last}(C_{p_0}^{Q_{0,0}}))$.